

OPEN WOUNDS

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ANNOTATION

This article discusses the types of care provided to patients, the types of injuries, their classification, and the processes of their treatment, in addition to knowing how to perform medical procedures. It also discusses the need for a modern nurse to be able to identify and address the psychological and social problems that may arise due to the patient's illness and to direct all efforts in society to eliminate these problems.

Keywords: Wounds, antiseptics, surgery, sutures, bleeding

An **injury** refers to a mechanical disruption of the integrity of the skin or mucous membranes, and sometimes of deeper tissues or internal organs

The risk of injury depends on:

- The amount of blood transferred
- The degree of development of traumatic shock
- Local or general infection developed
- Organs necessary for life damaged

Clinic of the injury :

General: Acute anemia
Shock

Infection

Members' life activities

violation

Local: Ogrik

Bleeding

opening of the wound edges

to stand

Bleeding from a wound:

- the sharper the instruments used to separate tissues , the more blood will flow from the wound

It's so strong that it's gone .

- Injuries do not always cause external bleeding.

The strength of the ogre depends on the following factors:

- The number of damaged receptors and nerve bundles
- The reactivity of the infected organism
- Depending on the nature of the weapon inflicting the injury and the speed of the injury

The degree of exposure of the wound edges is determined by the following:

- To the depth of the wound
- Disruption of the integrity of the skin's elastic fibers
- The size of the injury

Classification of injuries:

on the nature of tissue damage :

- ✓ gunshot wound
- ✓ Puncture wound

- ✓ Cut wound
- ✓ Cut wound
- ✓ A broken leg
- ✓ Crushed wound
- ✓ Laceration
- ✓ A broken bone
- ✓ Scratched wound
- ✓ Bite wound
- ✓ Poisoned wound
- ✓ Mixed injury

Depending on the cause of the injury :

- ✓ Operation
- ✓ Random

Depending on the location:

- ✓ Facial injury
- ✓ Head injury
- ✓ Neck injury
- ✓ Thoracic skull injury
- ✓ Corinne's injury
- ✓ Injury to the foot or ankle

Depending on the method of injury:

- Injuries resulting in primary traction
- Injuries resulting in secondary traction

Wound healing phases:

- Hydration (urticaria, temperature, edema, infiltration)
- Regeneration or dehydration

poor wound healing :

General :

- Adequate immune system underdevelopment
- Hypovitaminosis
- Chronic inflammatory diseases
- Diabetes mellitus
- Heart and kidney failure

Local :

- Damage to Large Blood Vessels
- Presence of foreign bodies in the wound
- Presence of necrotic tissue in the wound
- Bone sequestration
- Virulent microorganisms

2 types of wound healing :

- ❖ Wound healing (5-6 months)
- ❖ Secondary wound healing

Factors affecting the wound healing process:

- Connective tissue cells (fibroblasts, fibrocytes)
- A key intermediate substance related to water and electrolyte balance
- Collagen fibers

The opening of the wound edges within 3-9 days is not related to surgical infection, but to the following:

- ❖ Hypoproteinemia
- ❖ Hypovitaminosis
- ❖ Disturbance of water and electrolyte balance
- ❖ Disorders in the blood fibrinolytic system
- ❖ The state of the body's immunobiological forces

Causes of secondary wound healing:

Local :

- Loss of viability of wound margins
- Misalignment of the wound edges
- Large bush, presence of blood
- Presence of virulent infection

General :

- Cachexia
- Hypo or avitaminosis
- Metabolic disorders
- Infectious diseases

Granulation tissue layers:

- Leukocyte - necrotic (leukocytes)
- Vascular bed

(polyblasts and collagen fibers)

- Vertical Vascular Cavity

(fibroblasts, intercellular substance)

Causes of keloid scars:

- Nervous system disorders
- Endocrine system disorders
- Local circulatory failure

Injuries are divided into:

1. Aseptic
2. Bacterial – contaminated
3. Infected - an inflammatory clinic appears.
4. Purulent

Secondary infection occurs during first aid and treatment of the injured person.

aseptic, infected , and purulent wounds!

The method of treating injuries is determined based on the following:

- ❖ The time of the applicant 's application
- ❖ By type of injury
- ❖ The virulence of microorganisms entering the wound

It is used in the treatment of wounds:

- ✓ Operation and reconnection methods
- ✓ Local and general drug effects
- ✓ Physiotherapy treatments
- ✓ Therapeutic physical education

Treatment of various injuries:

- ❖ Treatment of surgical wounds (drainage, Redon drainage)
- ❖ Treatment of accidental injuries

A) Primary surgical treatment of the wound

B) When there is a wound infection in the wound, they are treated with secondary

surgical treatment is performed

C) Primary-delayed sutures

- ❖ Treatment of infected and purulent wounds

Step-by-step steps of primary surgical treatment of wounds

- Treating the wound area with antiseptic
- Anesthesia
- Washing the wound with antiseptics
- Hemostasis
- Injury revision
- Foreign body removal
- Cut and expand the wound

- Cutting and removing the edges and bottom of the wound
- Hemostasis
- Clean the wound with antiseptic agents
- Layered stitches to the wound, burn
- Aseptic dressing for wound

The following types of sutures are used in the treatment of purulent and infected wounds:

- Primary – delayed sutures are used to treat the wound after primary treatment.

It burns after 2-4 days.

- Secondary - early sutures are applied to a wound where granulation tissue has formed 2

It will burn after a week.

- Secondary - late stitches are removed after 3-4 weeks or later.

It is used in the treatment of wounds:

- ✓ Chemotherapy – antibiotics, sulfonamides.
- ✓ Laser therapy helium-neon laser, SO2 laser.
- ✓ Barotherapy - hyperbaric oxygenation, oxygenoberotherapy.
- ✓ In abacterial environments in an arotherapeutic device.
- ✓ Immunotherapy based on changes in immunological indicators .
- ✓ Diet therapy – high-calorie nutrition.
- ✓ Selective removal of certain toxins – hemosorption.
- ✓ Plasmapheresis – the removal of patient plasma and

replacement with donor plasma

Burn.

Primary surgical intervention (PSI) and its other types.

Primary surgical intervention (PSI) should be performed as soon as possible after the injury. In some cases, primary surgical intervention can be performed within 24-28 hours.

The anatomical structure of the wound should be taken into account. The skin on the head and face is spared, and if the blood vessels, nerves, and tendons are not damaged in the wound depth, they are not touched.

Bite wounds are extremely dangerous, given the risk of contracting rabies. To stop the growth of microorganisms, the following should be done.

1. To treat a wound with pulsating pressure using a fluid.
2. Vacuum and thoroughly wash the wound surface.
3. Ultrasound, injection of antiseptics and antibiotics into the wound at a speed of 20-50 Gs.
4. Cutting or steaming the contaminated area with a laser blade.

From the time the wound is healed to the time it is surgically removed and sutured, the following are distinguished:

1. The primary suture is either burned into a fresh wound or is performed within 24-28 hours until granulation tissue forms, in which case it is a delayed suture.

2. A secondary suture is applied to a granulating wound after it has been cleared of necrotic tissue. A suture applied after 2 weeks is called an early secondary suture.

The late secondary suture is removed after granulation and scar tissue has been excised, that is, after 3-4 weeks.

The primary suture is applied in layers in aseptic wounds. Usually, a knotted or continuous suture is used. In this case, all layers of the wound should be covered with the same depth and width. To obtain a cosmetic scar, the skin edges should be tightly sutured together. In the gastrointestinal tract, an Albert suture is performed from all layers, and a two-layer Lambert suture with serous muscle is performed.

Continuous sutures are used on surfaces that do not bear much weight, and they are divided into mirror-absorbing, cross-absorbing, and pouch-type. The skin sutures are removed 4 days after the operation, leaving a thin scar.

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